

Full Length Article

Measuring business impacts on the SDGs: a systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

The private sector must play a central role in advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To fulfill their duty, businesses must rely on accurate methodologies for measuring their impact on the SDGs. Since they were established, tools for evaluating companies' impact on the goals have proliferated. Over the last few years, there has been an increasing interest from academia in the evaluation of business impacts on the SDGs. The current study undertakes a systematic literature review to investigate the state-of-the-art of academic research on corporate SDG impact measurement. The review sampled 30 articles published between 2015 and 2022. Relying on qualitative content analysis and descriptive statistics, this study investigates the scope, purpose, main findings, and publication data of the articles of the sample, aiming to provide some structure to this novel field of research. Furthermore, this work identifies relevant gaps in the literature, providing some insights for future research.

Introduction

One of the most significant shifts in the global development agenda brought by the adoption of the SDGs was the foregrounding of the role of the private sector (Scheyvens et al., 2016). To begin with, the private sector has been at the heart of the Agenda 2030 since its inception. The design of the SDGs was conducted jointly by government, business, and civil society actors (Van Tulder et al., 2021). Besides, the agenda explicitly urges all actors to collaborate for achieving the 17 global goals (UN 2015). There is widespread agreement among experts that none of the SDGs can be attained without the committed participation of the private sector (Duran et al. 2018; Mio et al., 2020; Scheyvens et al., 2016). This heightened recognition of the need for co-creating development pathways between private, public, and civil society actors has been regarded as a paradigm shift in development thinking (Gore, 2015; UNGC 2015).

Businesses boast a series of strengths for delivering on the SDGs. To begin with, the private sector accounts for 70-85% of global investment (UN 2013), which places it in a unique position to hinder or contribute to attaining the global goals (Abe et al., 2019). Besides, businesses can contribute significantly to the SDGs by providing financing, know-how, technological innovation, managerial capacity, and a higher willingness

to take risks (Berrone et al., 2019; Scheyvens et al., 2016). Understanding the potential of the private sector for advancing the SDGs, however, requires recognizing its highly diverse nature. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) represent 90% of companies globally and account for 60-70% of jobs (UN 2022). These have an unmatched potential to provide breakthrough innovations since they can work outside of dominant paradigms and have weaker ties to existing products and technologies (Baumol, 2004; Kamal-Chaoui, 2017). Large companies, on the other hand, also have great potential for advancing the SDGs. In particular, the magnitude of the operations of multinational corporations (MNCs) gives them unrivaled leverage. MNCs produce 30% of the global GDP and 60% of the exports (De Backer and Mitoudot, 2018). Besides, they have a series of unique strengths, such as a global reach, access to cutting-edge technologies, and an unparalleled capacity to achieve large-scale solutions, which are all essential to advance the SDGs (Sachs, 2012).

Several studies have shown that there is a good level of understanding of the SDGs among corporations, and a strong commitment to work toward their achievement. As early as 2015, the results of a survey undertaken by PWC revealed that 92% of the global companies in the sample were aware of the SDGs and that 71% were already planning their response to the goals (Preston & Scott, 2015). Along the same line,

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a worldwide CEO survey undertaken in 2016 reported that 86% of managers interviewed “believe the SDGs provide an opportunity to rethink approaches to sustainable value creation”, and 70% of them “see the SDGs providing a clear framework to structure sustainability efforts” (UN GC & Accenture, 2016).

Over the last few years, however, numerous authors have called attention to the discrepancy between business commitment and action concerning the global agenda (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2023; Heras-Saizarbitoria et al., 2022; Van Tulder et al., 2021). In a recent qualitative study, Heras-Saizarbitoria et al. (2022) analyzed the sustainability reports of 1370 global companies. The authors concluded that most companies were “very evasive or silent about their approach to tackling the SDGs”, and that “The organizational operationalization of the SDGs was also superficial—or non-existent—in the majority of the cases”. In the same vein, van der Waal and Thijssens (2020) studied the sustainability reports of a sample of 1165 of the world’s largest corporations and found that only 23% of the companies mentioned the SDGs, and that details about how the global goals were operationalized were largely absent. Similarly, a report published by OXFAM revealed the existence of a marked discrepancy between global companies’ “talking” and “walking” in regard to the SDGs (Mhlanga et al., 2018). While approximately two-thirds of the 76 companies in their sample made public commitments about the global goals, only one-third disclosed information about SDG-related actions or targets (ibid). Lastly, although analyzing more restricted samples, the studies by (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2023) and (Manes-Rossi & Nicolo’, 2022) found that corporate engagement with the SDGs is in most cases symbolic rather than substantial, since commitments made by companies rarely translate into their long-term objectives and strategy.

An important factor to explain the divergence between business commitment and action concerning the global agenda is the difficulty of selecting adequate impact measurement tools (Martinuzzi & Schönherr, 2019; Schönherr et al., 2019). While it is clear that sustainability metrics are essential for businesses to guide decision-making and drive transformative change, (Liang et al., 2022; Schönherr et al., 2019), research has shown that most corporations have not yet adopted appropriate indicators to measure and manage their impact on the SDGs. For instance, Blasco et al. (2018) studied the world’s 250 largest companies and found that of those that report on their contribution to the global agenda, only 10% have set SMART performance goals in relation to the SDGs. Along the same line, Scott and McGill (2018) studied a sample of 729 global companies and noted that less than a quarter of them employ meaningful KPIs and targets related to the SDGs.

The insufficient corporate adoption of metrics linked to the SDGs contrasts starkly with its increasing availability. Since the adoption of the 2030 agenda, tools and indicators to measure the impact of business have proliferated (Liang et al., 2022; Schönherr et al., 2019). As Vogel-Pöschl (2020) describe it, there is now a wide array of tools for evaluating corporate impacts on the SDGs “ranging from simple checklists, guidance documents, and self-assessment tools, to complex indicator-based approaches covering supply chains, as well as product-related and indirect societal impacts.”. However, this rapidly-expanding toolbox has generated an opaque landscape, in which the information cost for comparing the different methodologies available is high (Liang et al., 2022; Schönherr et al., 2019). This situation represents a huge challenge both to managers, who struggle to decide which indicators are the most appropriate for decision-making, and stakeholders, who need to evaluate which methodologies are the most legitimate (ibid).

Over the last few years, there has been an increasing interest from academia in exploring the corporate SDG impact evaluation terrain. Several studies have been published reviewing the existing methods, proposing new metrics, or applying techniques developed in diverse fields to impact evaluation. These efforts have resulted in a heterogeneous and rapidly growing body of research. While a handful of studies have reviewed the existing standards for reporting corporate impacts on

the SDGs (Grainger-Brown & Malekpour, 2019; Mancini & Sala, 2018; Mansell et al., 2020), to the best of the authors’ knowledge no publication to date has systematically reviewed the academic production on this field. This gap in the literature holds significant relevance, particularly in light of the increasing proliferation of highly diverse academic works. The abundance of such works adds an additional challenge for practitioners who aim to navigate the complex landscape of corporate SDG impact measurement. Likewise, it poses a significant challenge for academics who strive to gain a comprehensive overview of the field’s progression. This study investigates the state-of-the-art of academic literature regarding methods to measure business impacts on the SDGs, aiming to bring some clarity and structure to this fast-developing field and to identify avenues for future research.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. First, the conceptual framework for the study is introduced. Second, the methodology adopted is thoroughly described. Third, the results of the study are presented and commented upon. Fourth, the implications of the findings are discussed. Finally, the conclusions of the study are presented, and insights for future research are provided.

Theoretical background

This section is structured in two parts. The first subsection introduces the concept of sustainable development, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the SDGs. The second subsection examines the concepts of impact assessment, sustainability assessment, and sustainability impact assessment, and explores how these relate to the myriad of tools and frameworks developed to measure the impact of business on sustainable development.

The sustainable development goals

The concept of sustainable development was first introduced in 1987 in the Burtland Report by the United Nations Commission on Environment and Development. The document defined sustainable development as “the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN, 1987). Subsequently, in 1997 the United Nations Agenda for Development expanded the definition building on Elkington (2002) triple bottom-line approach. The report stated that “Economic development, social development, and environmental protection are interdependent and mutually reinforcing components of sustainable development” (UN 1997). The notion of sustainable development has been a topic of heated debate in academia (Hopwood et al., 2005). It has been often critiqued for being vague, and its applicability has been questioned (Hopwood et al., 2005; Ruggerio, 2021). However, this concept has become hegemonic over the last decade (Ruggerio, 2021). It has been incorporated into international treaties, national constitutions, and corporate policies. It has also been widely adopted by civil society organizations, and it inspired several new fields of academic research (ibid).

In 2015, the 193 members of the United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, as a framework to guide the actions of a wide array of stakeholders on areas of critical importance for people and the planet (UN, 2015). At the heart of the Agenda are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a set of 17 interconnected and measurable goals, to be achieved by 2030. These are the result of an extensive participatory process and were designed to serve as a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all (UN, 2020). The introduction of the SDGs has been widely welcomed since these contribute to operationalizing the concept of sustainable development (Fonseca et al., 2020; Sachs, 2012). The 17 goals and their 169 associated targets constitute an overarching framework to guide the efforts of governments and non-state actors. These address a comprehensive array of global challenges, including poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice. A description of the 17

goals can be found on Table 1.

Business and sustainability impact assessment

A significant body of literature has been produced concerning the notions of sustainability assessment and impact assessment. In recent times, these two concepts have shown an increasing degree of association and interconnectedness (Ness et al., 2007; Waas et al., 2014). Studies vary in their approaches to examining the relationship between the two. Some authors view sustainability assessment as an overarching term that encompasses impact assessment (Hacking & Guthrie, 2008; Ness et al., 2007), while others perceive it as a distinct form of impact assessment that specifically focuses on sustainability issues (Bond et al., 2012).

Sustainability assessment (SA) is broadly defined as a tool that supports decision-making toward achieving sustainability objectives (Bond & Morrison-Saunders, 2013). Its purposes are defined by (Waas et al., 2014) as: information generation for decision-making; operationalization of the concept of sustainable development; forum for participation, debate, and deliberation; social learning; and structuring complexity. SA is often used as an umbrella term to refer to a variety of practices, methodologies, frameworks, and tools that focus on measuring sustainability at different scales (i.e. country, company, project, process)

Table 1
The sustainable development goals.

Sustainable Development Goals	Description
SDG 01. No poverty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End poverty in all its forms, everywhere
SDG 02. Zero hunger	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture
SDG 03. Good health and well-being	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages
SDG 04. Quality education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all
SDG 05. Gender equality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls
SDG 06. Clean water and sanitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure available and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all
SDG 07. Affordable and clean energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all
SDG 08. Decent work and economic growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all
SDG 09. Industry, innovation, and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and foster innovation
SDG 10. Reduced inequalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce inequality within and among countries
SDG 11. Sustainable cities and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable
SDG 12. Responsible consumption and production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
SDG 13. Climate action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts
SDG 14. Life below water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development
SDG 15. Life on land	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation, and halt biodiversity loss
SDG 16. Peace, justice, and strong institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels
SDG 17. Partnerships for the goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

Source:(UN 2017)

(Moldavska & Welo, 2019). There are examples of SA methodologies from a wide variety of fields, including engineering, public policies, business management, and urban planning, among others (Bond et al., 2015). Due to the plurality of stakeholders and theoretical perspectives that surround sustainable development, it is unlikely that a universally accepted and definitive SA process will emerge, beyond some fundamental basic steps (Bond et al., 2015).

Impact assessment (IA), on the other hand, is defined by the International Association for Impact Assessment as the process of identifying the future consequences of a current or proposed action (IAIA, 2020). This definition has been expanded by (Visser 2007), who incorporated the sustainable development dimension into it. The author conceptualized IA as “a process for ensuring that the possible future effects of a particular intervention [...] on the environment, society or the economy are and taken into account in decisions concerning the progression and implementation of that intervention”. (Visser, 2010, p. 231). Strictly speaking, the term IA is reserved for the ex-ante activity of predicting the outcomes of a specific project (Ness et al., 2007), while impact evaluation is used to refer to the ex-post assessment of outcomes of a policy or managerial decision (Pintér et al., 2012). However, these terms are often used interchangeably in practice (Waas et al., 2014).

SA and IA have been combined in the concept of Sustainability Impact Assessment (SIA). SIA is defined as “any process aiming to achieve sustainability goals and to make sustainability issues tangible and understandable based on a decision-guiding approach that helps to identify, structure, and evaluate the sustainability impact of past, current, and/or planned actions” (Trautwein, 2021). Metrics and indicators are at the heart of SIA, playing a fundamental role in monitoring progress toward sustainability goals, and assisting decision-making (Kumar et al., 2020). In the field of business, a wide array of frameworks and tools have been developed in the past decades to identify, measure, manage, and disclose the impacts of companies on sustainable development. Some of these tools are restricted to certain dimensions of sustainability (i.e. Carbon footprint), or to analyzing the impact of particular products or services (i.e. Life Cycle Assessment), while others offer comprehensive guidelines for assessing the sustainability impacts of entire companies (i.e. GRI Reporting Standards).

Over the last few years, the SDGs have been increasingly adopted as a framework by the leading institutions in the field of business sustainability impact assessment (Schönherr et al., 2019; Tavanti, 2023). A variety of tools have been released, ranging from user-friendly platforms to map and manage the SDG impacts of a particular company, such as B Lab’s SDG action Manager, to complex and exhausting guidance on the integration of the SDGs into the sustainability reporting of multinational corporations (UNGC and GRI, 2018). This growing adoption of the SDGs as an assessment framework for corporate sustainability impacts has been accompanied by a rapidly growing body of academic literature on the subject (Ferrero-Ferrero et al., 2023; Liang, Fernandez & Larsen, 2022; Schönherr and Martinuzzi 2019; Tsalis et al., 2020; Van Zanten & Huij, 2022).

Methodology

This study follows a systematic literature review (SLR) approach. As Littell et al. (2008) acknowledge, “A systematic review aims to comprehensively locate and synthesize research that bears on a particular question, using organized, transparent, and replicable procedures at each step in the process.”(p.1). The rigor associated with this methodology is generally considered a safeguard for minimizing the likelihood of error and bias in the review process (Booth et al., 2016; Lasserson et al., 2019; Littell et al., 2008).

This literature review followed the systematic methodology proposed by Tranfield et al., and Smart (2003), who built on the developments on SLRs that originated in the medical sciences, and developed a methodology specifically adapted to management and organizational studies. Their approach was deemed especially suitable

for this work since it has proved effective in several SLRs centered on the relationship between business and the SDGs (Boar et al., 2020; Kirst et al., 2021; Mio et al., 2020). Furthermore, this methodology has also been successfully employed in a number of works that explored the state-of-the-art of tools for assessing the impact of business on different dimensions of sustainable development (Morioka & de Carvalho, 2016; Pranugrahaning et al., 2021; Sassanelli et al., 2019).

This review followed the three stages outlined by Tranfield et al. (2003): planning the review; conducting the review; and reporting and dissemination. Table 2 depicts a summary of the activities associated with each stage.

Planning the review

During the planning stage, the first exercise was to develop a preliminary version of the research question. This question was iteratively reviewed and refined during this first stage. The formulation of the research question is a crucial endeavor since it provides the basis for structuring many of the successive steps, such as the selection of the search strategy, the definition of the inclusion criteria, the conduction of the synthesis, and the presentation of findings (Thomas et al., 2019). The final formulation of the research question is the following:

RQ: What is the state-of-the-art of academic production on business SDG impact evaluation?

Answering this question implies: 1) analyzing when and where relevant research was produced and published; 2) reviewing the research methods adopted in the literature; 3) surveying which SDGs have been addressed; 4) reviewing the aims of the existing studies; 5) synthesizing their main findings; and 5) identifying areas for further research.

The second step of the planning stage consisted in conducting a scoping literature search, in order to “assess the relevance and size of the literature and to delimit the subject area or topic.” (Tranfield et al., 2003). Trial-and-error searches with different combinations of keywords were conducted, as well as snowball-logic searches -reviewing the references of relevant studies-, following the strategy employed by Morioka and de Carvalho (2016) and Pranugrahaning et al. (2021). These initial searches were particularly useful for having a first grasp of the volume of academic literature on our field of interest, and for informing the choice of the study’s search strings.

The final step of the planning stage was centered on the preparation of the review protocol. The protocol contains detailed information about the questions addressed by the study, the search strategy, the criteria for inclusion and exclusion of references, the data extraction strategy, and the procedure for data analysis and synthesis (Booth et al., 2016; Littell et al., 2008; Tranfield et al., 2003). The review protocol is a key document in SLRs since it contains explicit descriptions of the criteria that guide the procedure and therefore contributes to protecting the

Table 2
Stages of a literature review.

Stage I - Planning the review
Phase 0 - Identification of the need for a review
Phase 1 - Preparation of a proposal for a review
Phase 2 - Development of a review protocol
Stage II - Conducting the review
Phase 3-Identification of research
Phase4- Selection of studies
Phase 5-Study quality assessment
Phase 6-Data extraction and monitoring progress
Phase 7-Data synthesis
Stage III - Reporting and dissemination
Phase 8- Report and recommendations
Phase 9- Getting evidence into practice

Source: (Tranfield et al., 2003)

objectivity and ensuring the replicability of the studies (Lasserson et al., 2019; Tranfield et al., 2003). A summary of the review protocol can be found in Table 3.

Conducting the review

The second stage of the SLR methodology developed by (Tranfield et al., 2003) is the core of the process, as it includes the review itself. The first step consisted in conducting searches in academic databases with the string defined at the planning stage. Scopus and Web of Science were the databases selected for this study due to their comprehensiveness. These sources have been extensively used in SLRs in the field of corporate sustainability (Kirst et al., 2021; Morioka & de Carvalho, 2016; Sassanelli et al., 2019). The search was restricted to articles published from 2015 onwards. Given the specific nature of this review, it was deemed highly improbable that any study published prior to the adoption of the global goals would offer significant insights to address our research question.

The final version of the search string can be found in Table 3. The string was designed to capture all the studies that include in their title, abstract, or keywords, the terms corporation, impact, measurement, and SDGs, or any of their synonyms. The search in the academic databases resulted in the identification of 1.214 studies in Scopus and 1.736 in Web of Science. Only studies in English were considered, following Mio et al. (2020) and Morioka and de Carvalho (2016). After removing duplicates and errors (i.e. non full-text articles), the size of the sample was 2.319 documents.

The second step of the review stage consisted of the screening of the articles’ titles, keywords, and abstracts, to check their eligibility. The criteria for including studies in the sample were intentionally broad, given the novelty of the research field under study. To be considered for the review, papers had to meet the following three conditions: (1) develop, apply, or review methodologies (2) for estimating the impact of business (3) on the SDGs. In those cases in which it was not clear from the screening whether the articles complied with the inclusion criteria, a full reading of the introduction, methodology, and conclusion was performed (Morioka & de Carvalho, 2016; Pranugrahaning et al., 2021). Following the criterion of (Kirst et al., 2021), books were excluded. After the initial screening, a total of 65 articles were selected for further reading.

The third step of the review stage involved reading the full text of the documents. At this point, it was reassessed whether the articles met the inclusion criteria, in order to discard those that were not truly informative to the review question. A total of 30 studies were selected for further analysis after this round.

The data were examined using a qualitative content analysis approach. The structuring content analysis technique described by Mayring (2015) was followed for filtering out, synthesizing, and

Table 3
Summarized review protocol.

Review question	What is the state-of-the-art of methodologies used for SDG impact evaluation in businesses in academic literature?
Search string	TTT-ABS-KEY - (((business OR corpor* OR private OR company OR organization OR firm OR enterprise OR mnc OR mne OR tnc) AND (impact* OR effect* OR outcome OR influence) AND (sdgs OR {sustainable development goals}) AND (evaluat* OR measur* OR apprais* OR estimat* OR assess* OR gaug* OR quantif*))
Databases	Scopus, Web of Science
Inclusion criteria	Studies that develop, apply, or review methodologies (1) for estimating the impact of business (2) on the SDGs(3).
Data extraction categories	1-Basic publication data: name of the journal, year of publication, country of researcher’s institutional affiliation 2- Scope data: SDGs covered, Industries analyzed, type of companies analyzed 3-Content data: Aims of the study, methods adopted, main findings.

analyzing the particular aspects of the studies that were relevant to answering the research question. The categories of data to be extracted from the documents were defined a priori, as it is common practice in studies that apply structuring content analysis (Kohlbacher, 2006; Mayring, 2015).

The following three classes of data were defined for this study:

- 1- Basic publication data: keywords, authors, journal, year of publication, and country of the main researcher’s institutional affiliation.
- 2- Scope data: SDGs covered, Industries analyzed, and size of the companies analyzed
- 3- Content data: Aims of the study, methods applied, and main findings.

The data analysis started in parallel to the full-text reading of the articles. The texts were coded and relevant fragments were extracted according to the defined categories. The extracted data was organized on an electronic spreadsheet for facilitating its analysis, following Morioka and de Carvalho (2016). Subsequently, a series of descriptive statistics were performed based on the publication and scope data, to obtain an initial overview of the literature sample. The fragments of content data extracted from the sample were then analyzed, and the broad a priori-defined categories were refined into narrower sub-categories (Mayring, 2015).

Reporting and dissemination

Finally, the diffusion stage of the SLR process was conducted. The review process, analysis, and findings were documented in this article, with the aim of disseminating its results.

Results

This section provides an overview of the publication data of the sample of articles included in this study, followed by an analysis of the scope, methods, aims, and results of the publications. The list of studies included in the review can be found in the Appendix.

General overview of the literature

The first step of the analysis consisted of computing descriptive statistics, based on the basic publication data extracted from the articles, to gain an initial overview of the sample. Fig. 1 shows the yearly evolution of the publications. The most remarkable feature of the literature is its novelty. 26 of the 30 articles in the sample (86%) were published from 2020 onwards. Furthermore, the number of academic publications related to measuring business impacts on the SDGs grew exponentially

Fig. 1. Number of articles in the sample by year of publication, Source: own elaboration.

between 2017 and 2021. It is not clear if this trend continued in 2022 since this study covered only studies published up to June 2022.

Table 4 shows the journals where the articles in the sample were published. Sustainability is the leading journal on the topic under analysis. Eight of the sampled articles were published in this journal. The remaining twenty-two articles were all published by different publications. The thematic profile of the journals of the sample is highly diverse, with publications belonging to the fields of environmental sciences, business, economics, development studies, engineering, computer science, public administration, chemistry, and social sciences, among others. The research areas of the journals in the sample are listed in Table 4.

The average number of citations of the papers reviewed on the Web of Science databases was 7.4. This metric suggests that the literature analyzed is having a relevant impact despite its novelty (Pizzi et al., 2020). The most widely cited articles are Johnsson et al. (2020) review of sustainability reporting tools, which has received 29 citations and Hacking’s (2019) study on the assessment of the impact of capital projects, which has received 23 citations. These studies are followed by van der Waal and Thijssens’s (2020) methodology to assess the impact of

Table 4
Journals in the sample.

Journal	Research area	Number of Publications
Sustainability	Environmental Sciences & Ecology	8
ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering	Chemistry, Engineering	1
Acta Innovations	Energy & Fuels; Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Ad-Minister	Business & Economics	1
Applied Sciences - Basel	Chemistry; Engineering; Materials Science; Physics	1
Business Ethics	Business & Economics; Social Sciences	1
CSR and Environmental Management	Business & Economics; Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Electronics	Science & Technology; Engineering	1
Frontiers in sustainable food systems	Food Science & Technology	1
Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal	Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Information	Computer Science	1
Information Technology for Development	Computer Science; Development Studies	1
International Journal of Economics and Business Administration	Business & Economics	1
Journal of Cleaner Production	Science & Technology - Other Topics; Engineering; Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Journal of Environmental Planning and Management	Development Studies; Public Administration	1
Palgrave Communications	Social Sciences - Other Topics	1
Procedia Cirp	Science & Technology - Other Topics; Engineering	1
Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	Science & Technology - Other Topics; Energy & Fuels	1
Science of the Total Environment	Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Sustainable Development	Development Studies; Science & Technology - Other Topics; Public Administration	1
The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment	Engineering; Environmental Sciences & Ecology	1
Water Resources Management	Engineering; Water Resources	1
Journal of Evaluation	Social Sciences - Other Topics	1
Total		30

corporate innovation by analyzing patent applications, and Vanham and Mekonnen's (2021) review of water use indicators. These articles received 22 citations each. It is worth noting that a high proportion of the studies in the sample were published close to the date when this review was conducted (See Fig. 1). Therefore, the number of citations of the most recent papers in the sample is not an accurate indicator of their influence in the long term. Data on the citations of the sampled papers is presented in the Appendix.

Table 5 shows the origin of the studies sampled. The criterium used for determining the origin of each article was the country of the institutional affiliation of the first author. The overwhelming majority of the papers in the sample are of European origin (23). The rest of the articles were from North America (3), South America (3), and Asia (1). Within Europe, Germany and the United Kingdom were the countries with the most contributions, with 4 studies each, followed by Italy (3), Spain (3), and Norway (2). In the Americas, Brazil and the United States were the countries with the most publications, with two each, followed by Canada and Colombia, with one publication. Only one Asian study, from Taiwan, was included in the sample. Lastly, the sample did not include any study from Africa or Oceania.

Scope of the literature

This subsection presents the results of the investigation of the scope of the sampled articles. The first dimension analyzed was the article's coverage of the 17 SDGs. 14 of the selected studies (47%) covered the global agenda entirely. These studies undertake a broad but shallow analysis of the global goals. The other 16 studies in the sample (53%) focus on a subset of the SDGs. Within this class, 10 articles analyze a group of SDGs, and 6 studies focus on a single goal. Unlike the articles of the former group, studies of this kind dig deeper into the specifics of measuring corporate impact on individual goals and targets. As shown in Fig. 2, the attention received by the different SDGs in the studies that focus on specific goals varied greatly. While some goals were addressed by many studies, such as SDGs 7, 8, 9, and 12 (4 studies), other goals such as SDGs 11, 14, 15, and 17 received little to no attention. This pattern is in line with the findings of (Liang, Fernandez & Larsen, 2022), who highlight the lack of attention received by SDGs 11 and 14 in corporate impact assessment methods. The list of the SDGs analyzed by each of the studies of the sample is available in the Appendix.

Concerning the sectoral focus of the studies, half of the sample focus on particular industries. The sectors analyzed are highly varied. These

Table 5
Number of studies in the sample by country and region.

Region	Country	Number of studies
Europe	Germany	4
	United Kingdom	4
	Italy	3
	Spain	3
	Norway	2
	Austria	1
	Denmark	1
	Netherlands	1
	Poland	1
	Portugal	1
	Sweden	1
	Ukraine	1
	North America	United States
Canada		1
South America	Brasil	2
	Colombia	1
Asia	Taiwan	1

include¹: construction (2), water and wastewater treatment (2), waste management (1), agriculture(1), aquaculture (1), information technology (1), telecommunications (1), energy generation (1), land transport (1), geotechnical engineering (1), ICT component manufacturing (1), paper Industry (1), automobile industry (1), laminated timber production (1), and the pharmaceutical industry (1). The other half of the studies in the sample review, apply or develop methodologies that are not specific to a particular sector. As for the classes of firms analyzed, seven studies focus on MNCs, seven studied companies operating from a single country, one focused on SMEs, and the remaining fifteen do not explicitly center on a particular type of firm.

Lastly, the studies in the sample were classified according to their unit analysis. Twelve of the articles looked at global or regional value chains, twelve focused on individual companies, and six studies focused on particular projects, processes, products, or technologies within a company.

Methods adopted in the literature

The methods adopted in the works studied are presented in Table 6. The most noteworthy features of the sample are the high number of studies that undertook conceptual developments (19), and the few works that undertook case studies (4). The details about the methods applied in each individual work can be found in the Appendix.

Aims and main findings of the sampled articles

This subsection presents the results of the analysis of the aims and the main findings of the articles included in the sample. The literature sample was divided into three broad groups according to the main purpose of each article with respect to corporate SDG impact measurement: (A) studies that primarily focus on reviewing existing tools or methodologies; (B) studies that primarily focus on applying existing tools or methodologies, and (C) studies that primarily focus on developing new tools or methodologies.

Studies aimed at reviewing existing tools or methodologies

Group A represents roughly one-third of the sample (11 articles). The most cohesive and developed research line within this group consists of a collection of four works that study the challenges of measuring the impacts of business on the SDGs and the shortcomings of the existing methodologies, from a macro perspective. In other words, these studies undertake a high-level analysis of the challenges of measuring business impacts on the global goals, without digging into the particularities of specific industries or organizations. Regarding the challenges found by these papers, the most prevalent concern is SDG Washing, which refers to the practice of engaging with the SDGs to enhance the legitimacy of an organization, rather than for improving its sustainability performance (Heras-Saizarbitoria et al., 2022). In this respect, Johnsson et al. (2020) and Vogel-Pöschl et al. (2020) highlight the contradictory nature of current SDG impact measurement approaches: while these offer companies meaningful inputs for managing their transition towards sustainability, they also open the possibility of camouflaging business-as-usual. Furthermore, "cherry-picking", is signaled as an especially harmful trend in corporate impact assessments (Johnsson et al., 2020; Kornieieva, 2020). This term refers to the practice of focusing assessments on targets in which a company is performing well, or in those in which it could perform well easily (Ibid). In this vein, Diaz-Sarachaga's (2021) insightful empirical work shows the existence of a stark inconsistency between the sustainability disclosures and actions performed by four leading Spanish MNCs. In another vein, a crucial challenge identified by Vogel-Pöschl et al. (2020) is the complexity of approaching the global value chains of MNCs, since these are not clearly

¹ Some studies analyze more than one industry.

Fig. 2. Number of studies that specifically address each SDG, Source: own elaboration.

Table 6
Methods adopted in the sample.

Methods	Number of studies
Conceptual development	19
Literature review	9
Qualitative content analysis	6
Case study	4
Analysis of geographic information	1

delimited, and typically span across multiple locations, jurisdictions, branches, and industries.

On the other hand, the main shortcomings of current methods for measuring firmsSDG impacts that were identified in the literature include: the lack of comparability and benchmarking between companies belonging to different sectors (Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021), or which employ different methodologies in their assessments (Kornieieva, 2020), the insufficient use of data assurance mechanisms (Kornieieva, 2020; Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020), the uneven representation of the 2030 agenda on the impact measurement frameworks (Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021), the absence of systems concepts in the design of the methodologies (Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020), and the infrequent use of tools to uncover impact pathways (Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020).

The rest of the studies of group A constitute a heterogeneous and highly specific collection of works. Two of the articles review metrics to measure the sustainability performance of businesses on specific goals: (Gomez-Trujillo et al., 2021; Vanham & Mekonnen, 2021)) develop a critique of a specific indicator to measure business impact on SDG 6, and Gomez-Trujillo et al. (2021) review the metrics used to report on SDG 12 by a sample of 854 companies. The rest of the studies in group A review specific frameworks to analyze the SDG impact of business from highly varied perspectives. To begin, Wilson (2021) reviews the Social and Human Capital Protocol and discusses possible applications of that framework for SDG impact measurement. Secondly, Bojarska et al. (2021) explore the potential of Life Cycle Assessment methods to assist the measuring firms’ impacts on the global goals. Additionally, Mansell et al. (2020), review a methodology for measuring and managing the SDG impacts of infrastructure investments from a project perspective (Mansell et al., 2020). Lastly, (Ordonez-Ponce & Khare, 2021) study focuses on analyzing the suitability of GRI 300 as an SDG impact measurement tool in the automobile industry.

Studies aimed at exploring the application of existing tools and methodologies

Group B comprises 23% of the sample (7 studies). Within this subset, two categories of articles can be identified. The first one is formed by

studies that focus on the application of highly specific pre-existing frameworks. For instance, Becchetti Semplici (2021) analyze the application of the NeXt Index for SDG impact evaluation. This tool was developed by a homonymous NGO, to which two of the authors of the study are affiliated. The index is defined as a “living multi-stakeholder community-based indicator, developed through participatory processes and co-design between statistical experts, end-users, and relevant stakeholders”. Similarly, Giannetti et al. (2022) review the application of the Five Sector Sustainability Model (5SEnSU) for analyzing the sustainability performance of water and wastewater treatment companies in Brazil. The 5SEnSU tool, developed by most of the authors of the sampled study, is a framework based on the input-state-output model. Its aim is to simplify the relationships between the environment, society, and economy, for assisting sustainability assessments. Likewise, Jarosch et al. (2020) apply the RESPONSA framework to analyze the sustainability impact of laminated timber production. The applied tool was developed by some of the co-authors of the sampled article, to study the social impact of wood-based value chains (ibid). According to (Pizzi et al., 2020) the proliferation of studies that apply frameworks developed in researchers’ individual areas of expertise to the study of the relationship between business and the SDGs is a symptom of the lack of a consolidated theory in this field.

The second category of articles within group B is composed of studies that apply proven tools and methodologies, with the aim of strengthening current approaches to incorporate SDG evaluation in particular industries. For instance, Prieto-Egido et al. (2022) employ the theory of change framework, a widely used tool in the development evaluation field, complemented with sector-specific impact literature, in order to assess the impact of a company that provides telecommunication services in rural areas of Perú., In parallel, Secher et al. (2018) apply Life Cycle Assessment concepts to aid the identification and evaluation of construction firms’ SDG impacts. Similarly, Berger et al. (2021) explore the application of the Water Footprint as a tool to measure and manage industrial impacts on SDG 6.

Studies aimed at developing novel tools or methodologies

Lastly, with 12 articles Group C is the largest one of the sample (40%). Within this subset, which is distinguished by the highly specific nature of its studies, two main lines of work can be identified. The first and largest collection comprises works that develop tools to measure the impact of specific industries on the SDGs. The second, and more incipient line of research, consists of articles that focus on developing frameworks for assessing the impacts of the corporate adoption of specific technologies on the SDGs.

The first line of research within group C can be divided into two categories according to its studies’ coverage of the SDGs. The first one

consists of works that focus on evaluating the impact of specific industries on the global agenda as a whole. [Abualtaher et al. \(2021\)](#), for instance, develop a framework to integrate SDG measurement and management into the Norwegian salmon value chain. [Deamer et al. \(2021\)](#) on the other hand, propose and apply a methodology to measure the SDG impacts of geotechnical engineering companies, by disentangling, categorizing, and assigning scores to the different processes involved in their activity. Likewise, [Hu et al. \(2016\)](#) develop and test a framework for analyzing the SDG impacts of ICT companies in Taiwan. Within the same research line, the second category of studies is more narrow-focused. Articles of this class center on developing frameworks to measure the SDG impact of particular industries on specific goals or targets. [Roschangar et al. \(2022\)](#), for example, develop an indicator to support pharmaceutical companies in measuring and managing their resource efficiency in their drug synthesis processes and tracking their contribution to SDG12. Likewise, [Buonocore et al. \(2019\)](#) develop a model based on country-level publicly available data, to evaluate the impact of investments on more efficient technologies for land transport and electricity generation, on pollution-related deaths (SDG 3, Target 3.9, Indicator 3.9.1). Additionally, [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#) develop context-sensitive metrics to assess the sustainability impact of industrial water use.

The second and minor line of research within group C approaches SDG impact measurement from a technological perspective. [Sætra, \(2021\)](#) for instance, presents a framework for understanding and measuring the SDG impact of the corporate applications of artificial intelligence. Along the same line, [Costa et al. \(2022\)](#) develop and apply a methodology for mapping and assessing the impacts of firms' adoption of digital technologies on the global goals. Lastly, in a different sphere, [Mottet et al. \(2020\)](#) propose a tool that enables the estimation of the impact of the application of agroecological practices on the SDGs.

Discussion: Making sense of the literature

The aims of this paper were to synthesize the academic literature on corporate SDG impact measurement, give structure to this emerging field of research, and identify gaps in the literature. By pursuing these objectives, this work aims to aid researchers in identifying future lines of work and to provide practitioners with a comprehensive overview of the academic discussion on SDG impact measurement.

The study of the publication data of the articles in the sample offered an insightful snapshot into the state of academic production on business SDG impact evaluation. Three defining features of the literature emerged from this stage of the analysis. First, research in this field is highly concentrated geographically. 86% of the studies were authored by researchers affiliated with European institutions. Furthermore, just 4 countries concentrated half of the studies in the sample. Second, research on corporate SDG impact measurement is remarkably recent. 77% of the works in the corpus were published from 2020 onwards. Third, the literature on business SDG impact measurement stems from a wide range of disciplines. The thirty studies sampled for this analysis were published across 23 distinct journals, encompassing a diverse array of research areas. These insights were crucial for setting the context for interpreting the results of the second stage of this study.

Challenges vs. solutions

Relevant insights were also gained from the study of the content of the sampled articles. The first takeaway was the existence of a divergence between the challenges identified by researchers who performed reviews of existing measurement tools from a macro perspective, and the highly industry-specific solutions developed by academics working from a micro angle. Studies of the former group conducted high-level analyses of the challenges of business SDG impact measurement and of the structural flaws of existing tools. These emphasized the importance of addressing practices such as SDG-washing and cherry-picking, and

challenges such as the lack of assurance mechanisms, the difficulty of benchmarking across industries, and the complexity of assessing impacts across global value chains. Conversely, studies of the latter group focused on applying tools to measure the SDG impacts of highly-specific sectors (i.e. salmon value chain, laminated timber production, geotechnical engineering), or developing methods to assess the impact of specific activities on particular SDGs (i.e. impact of land transport on target 3.9, impact of drug synthesis on SDG 12). As shown in [Table 7](#), the challenges identified by macro-level studies received limited or no attention in the articles of the sample that adopted a micro perspective.

To begin, no study approached the challenge of measuring SDG impacts across the global and highly complex value chains of MNCs. Improving our understanding of this question is essential, given the scale of MNCs' operations, and the central role they are required to play in advancing the SDGs. Similarly, none of the works in the studied corpus focused on the uneven representation of the global agenda on the existing methodologies to assess business impacts on the SDGs. As shown by [Diaz-Sarachaga \(2021\)](#), the GRI Standards cover only 36% of the SDG targets, and the SAM CSA -Dow Jones methodology covers 23%. Therefore these tools provide only a limited outlook on firms' impacts on the global agenda (*ibid*). This flaw is highly relevant since the frameworks analyzed by [Diaz-Sarachaga \(2021\)](#) are some of the most widely used for corporate sustainability reporting. Lastly, no study addressed the insufficient adoption of data assurance mechanisms in existing SDG impact reporting tools. Tackling this shortcoming is crucial for improving the legitimacy of SDG assessment methods.

If we look at those studies that did approach the challenges of measuring business SDG impacts and the shortcomings of existing methodologies, the picture is not overly encouraging. To begin with, only two studies suggest possible avenues for tackling SDG Washing. These works propose solutions to address the mentioned issue in specific domains. On the one hand, [Johnsson et al. \(2020\)](#) suggest three general principles to avoid SDG washing when evaluating business impacts on SDG 13 (See [Table 7](#)). On the other hand, [Kornieieva \(2020\)](#) proposes a novel indicator to reflect the environmental sustainability of corporate investments in fixed capital assets. While the attention given by these authors to SDG Washing is a positive sign, it is evident that further studies in the area are needed.

On a more positive note, two studies contribute to overcoming the insufficient use of tools for uncovering impact pathways by employing the Theory of Change method (ToC), a widely used tool for impact evaluations in the development and policy field, proposed by ([Weiss, 1995](#)). The ToC method consists of detailing how a certain activity or intervention is understood to produce a set of results, which in turn contribute to achieving certain impacts ([Rogers, 2014](#)). In the first place, [Prieto-Egido et al. \(2022\)](#), combine the ToC combined with the Digital-for-Development paradigm, to investigate the impact of the provision of telecommunication services in rural areas of Peru. Secondly, [Mansell et al. \(2020\)](#) employ the SDG Infrastructure Impact Value Chain, a specialized methodology based on the ToC framework, for exploring the impacts of infrastructure projects. Besides, two studies address the need for SDG impact benchmarking. [Vanham and Mekonen \(2020\)](#), on the one hand, propose two benchmarks to evaluate water use in irrigated wheat production. [Giannetti et al. \(2022\)](#), on the other, develop a series of indicators linked to the SDGs to enable the benchmarking of the sustainability performance of water and wastewater treatment companies. Lastly, the 5SEnSU model applied by [Giannetti et al. \(2022\)](#), and the Systems Engineering Six-step Method adopted by [Abualtaher et al. \(2021\)](#), are conceived from a systems perspective, which constitutes an encouraging trend.

Notwithstanding the aforementioned efforts for tackling the challenges of measuring business SDG impacts and the shortcomings of existing methodologies, studies that address these issues are a small proportion of the sample. Besides, the solutions proposed by these works are in most cases sector and goal specific. Hence, the development of more studies in this area is crucial for contributing to the consolidation

Table 7
Challenges, shortcomings, and proposed solutions.

Challenges & Shortcomings	Studies that identify the issue	Studies that explicitly address the issue	Type of solutions proposed
Complexity of MNCs value chains	Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	None	-
Uneven representation of the 2030 agenda	Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021	None	-
SDG Washing/Cherry picking	Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021; Johnsson et al., 2020; Kornieieva, 2020; Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	-Johnsson et al. (2020) propose three principles for avoiding SDG-Washing in goal 13: 1-adopting a value chain perspective, 2-Setting clear targets in line with the Paris Agreement, and 3- Including other SDGs related to climate change into evaluations. -Kornieieva (2020) proposes the Investment Priority Ratio, which reflects the proportion of a company's fixed capital investments that are "green". $IPR = (\text{Green capital investments} / \text{total capital investments}) \times 100$	-Proposal of new reporting principles -Novel indicator
Insufficient use of system concepts	Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	- Giannetti et al. (2022) adopts the <i>FIVE SEctor Sustainability (5SEnSU)</i> model, which was developed with a systems perspective, for evaluating the impacts of water and wastewater treatment companies in Brazil. -Abualtaher et al. (2021) employ the <i>Systems Engineering Six-step Method</i> for evaluating the impacts of the Norwegian salmon value chain on the SDGs.	-Application of highly specific existing framework -Application of highly specific existing framework
Lack of comparability/ benchmarking	Kornieieva, 2020; Prieto-Egido et al., 2022; Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021	-Giannetti et al. (2022) develop a series of indicators related to the SDGs to enable the benchmarking of some aspects of the sustainability performance of water and wastewater treatment companies. i.e. Ratio CO2 emissions per year from sewage treatment=(tons CO2-eq/m3 year). -Vanham and Mekonen (2020) apply two benchmarks for evaluating water use in irrigated wheat production: the global 50th percentile (1391 m3/ton), and a second value weighted by the aridity of each analyzed zone.	-Novel benchmark -Novel benchmark
Infrequent use of tools for uncovering impact pathways.	Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	-Prieto-Egido et al. (2022) combine the <i>Theory of Change</i> methodology combined with the <i>Digital-for-Development</i> paradigm, to investigate the impact of the provision of telecommunication services in rural areas of Peru. -Mansell et al. (2020) employ the <i>SDG Infrastructure Impact Value Chain</i> , a tool based on the <i>Theory of Change</i> methodology, for exploring the impacts of infrastructure projects.	-Existing framework -Existing highly specific framework
Insufficient use of external data assurance	Kornieieva, 2020, Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	None	-

Source: own elaboration

of the field.

A fragmented body of knowledge

A second relevant insight gained from the analysis was that the field of corporate SDG impact evaluation is characterized by its fragmentation. Rather than a cohesive body of work, where researchers build upon previous studies in the field, the corpus analyzed can be described as a heterogeneous and loosely connected collection of articles. It was not possible to identify dominant approaches to business SDG impact measurement in the sample studied.

As shown in the previous section, the majority of the studies consist of developments or applications of highly specific methodologies for either estimating the SDG impact of particular industries or measuring the impact of business on a specific target. This finding is in line with the results of Pizzi et al. (2020). These authors undertook a systematic literature review of academic articles addressing the relationship between business and the global agenda and concluded that there is no consolidated theoretical framework to address the SDGs from a business perspective. As a result, individual researchers tend to approach the global goals by adopting specific frameworks from their own disciplines, which does not contribute to the theoretical consolidation of the field (ibid). As presented previously, this trend is evident in the field of corporate SDG impact evaluation. Two factors might be behind the fragmented nature of the literature studied. One of them is the aforementioned novelty of the research field. Another possibility is that the proliferation of highly specialized and loosely connected models is a consequence of the kind of problem that researchers face. Measuring the SDG impacts of industries operating in particular contexts and within distinct value chains is an intrinsically complex and singular endeavor.

Limitations

This work has two distinct limitations. Firstly, it focused exclusively on the analysis of academic literature. The authors are aware of the existence of a large and fast-expanding body of gray literature on corporate SDG impact evaluation, coming mainly from international institutions, consulting firms, and think tanks. It would be interesting to study the state-of-the-art of gray literature on the topic in future works, and how it relates to academic production in the field. In the second place, even if this study followed a strict systematic review protocol, and the search string was iteratively tested and refined, it is possible that some relevant studies were not captured in the sample.

Recommendations for future research

In light of the above, we suggest that for fostering the development of the discipline of corporate SDG impact measurement it is necessary to nurture a new layer of studies, between the macro diagnostics of the challenges of the field, and the micro-level, highly-specific solutions. The emergence of new research centered on understanding and overcoming the obstacles to corporate SDG impact measurement is essential for bridging the micro and macro bodies of work. This would greatly contribute to enhancing the cohesiveness and robustness of this rapidly-growing field. In particular, studies that address issues such as SDG-Washing, global value chains, and benchmarking across industries and standards are greatly needed. These would serve as a solid foundation for researchers working from a micro perspective to build upon.

Lastly, it is also essential to expand the geographic diversity of this novel field of study. Given the global nature of the 2030 Agenda and the importance of local contexts for understanding sustainability challenges and conceiving solutions to these, it is of paramount importance to attract researchers working from more diverse regions to this emerging

discipline.

Implications for practitioners

This work offers an overview of the academic production on business SDG impact measurement to practitioners in the field of corporate sustainability. As shown, the literature is highly fragmented and specialized, and there are no dominant methodologies. Yet, some general insights to inform practice can be derived. First, practitioners interested in measuring the impact of their organizations on the SDGs can find support in academic studies when scoping their assessment efforts. The literature analyzed provides clues on how to approach impact measurement in various scales, ranging from a given technology within a company to a regional value chain. Secondly, this work reviews the conceptual models currently used by academics to identify impact chains, such as the theory of change and life cycle assessment methods. These can provide great value for framing measurement endeavors. Besides, this work provides practitioners with a summary of the main challenges to measuring business SDG impact. Lastly, this study introduces some of the ethical considerations that surround sustainability measurement in business settings, by discussing practices such as SDG-washing and cherry-picking.

Conclusion

This study conducted a systematic literature review with the objective of critically examining the academic production on business SDG impact measurement. Its contributions are threefold. First, this work provides structure to this emerging field of research. Second, this study identifies gaps in the literature and suggests potential avenues for future research. Third, this work offers practitioners an overview of the academic literature on corporate SDG impact assessment, facilitating their navigation of this rapidly growing body of knowledge. Additionally, it equips them with insights into the tools available for scoping impact measurement endeavors and presents them with the most widely used conceptual developments to frame these efforts.

The first phase of this study consisted of a statistical analysis of the publication data of the sampled articles. The descriptive statistics produced provide a valuable overview of the current state of the field. Three main features of the literature stood out. Firstly, research in this area is remarkably new. 86% of the studies were published from 2020 onwards. Secondly, the academic production in this field has a high level of geographical concentration. 77 % of the studies came from researchers affiliated with European Universities. In the third place, research on the topic under analysis comes from highly varied disciplines. The papers in the sample were published in research journals spanning various fields, including environmental sciences, engineering, energy, business, economics, computer science, development studies, and chemistry, among others.

The second phase of this study consisted on the analysis of the aims and main findings of the sampled publications following a structuring content analysis approach. Two main takeaways were derived from this

Appendix

Methodology and SDGs coverage of the articles sampled

Authors	Title	Methods	Group	Methodology description	SDGs covered	Citations-WoS databases
Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021	Shortcomings in reporting contributions towards the sustainable development goals	Content analysis	A	Textual analysis and descriptive statistics of GRI and SAM CSA- Dow	All	9

(continued on next page)

stage. First, our analysis suggests that there is a divergence between the challenges to business SDG impact measurement identified by researchers working at a macro level and the solutions proposed by academics working from a micro perspective. While scholars of the former group highlight the need of advancing our understanding of the core challenges of SDG impact measurement, such as SDG-Washing, benchmarking across industries, and addressing global value chains, researchers of the latter group gave limited attention to these issues. Instead, most of the academics of the second group focus on developing and applying highly specific methodologies for measuring the impact of particular industries on selected SDGs. Secondly, the fragmentation of the literature emerged as a key feature of the body of research examined. No dominant approaches to business SDG impact measurement were identified in the sample studied. Rather than a cohesive body of work, where researchers build upon previous studies in the field, the literature sample analyzed can be described as a heterogeneous and loosely connected collection of highly specialized studies.

In light of the above, we suggest that a new layer of studies centered on understanding and overcoming the structural challenges of measuring corporate SDG impacts is needed to contribute to the theoretical consolidation of the field. This would be instrumental for bridging the research produced at the macro and micro levels, thereby enhancing the cohesiveness of academic production on this subject. Furthermore, improving our understanding of those challenges would play a crucial role in improving the robustness of future measurement methodologies. Lastly, we strongly believe that incorporating research from regions beyond Europe would be immensely enriching for the discipline, as it would facilitate the inclusion of diverse perspectives in the development of the field.

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(continued)

Authors	Title	Methods	Group	Methodology description	SDGs covered	Citations-WoS databases
Kornieieva, 2020	Non-financial Reporting Challenges in Monitoring SDG's Achievement: Investment Aspects for Transition Economy	Literature review	A	Jones Sustainability Index annual reports. Comparison of indicators proposed by GRI Standards, SASB Standards, and UNCTAD Guide.	7, 8, 9 10, 17	10
Vogel-Pöschl et al., 2020	Evaluating Corporate Impacts on the SDGs – Tools, Cases, and Future Challenges	Content analysis	A	Qualitative content analysis of publicly available documents. A sample of 170 tools suggested by a group of experts is adopted. In-depth analysis of SDG Compass, B impact assessment, SAFA, Natural Capital Protocol, and LBG Model.	All	0
Johnsson et al., 2020	The framing of a sustainable development goals assessment in decarbonizing the construction industry – Avoiding “Greenwashing”	Literature review	A	Systematic Literature review & Text Analysis. In-depth analysis of Ramboll -SDG Impact Assessment, PWC- Navigating the SDGs business guide, KPMG-SDG Industry Matrix, GRI & UNGC- SDG Compass and Business, and the SDG Impact Assessment Tool of the Gothenburg Centre for Sustainable Development	13	29
Ordonez-Ponce & Khare, 2021	GRI 300 as a measurement tool for the United Nations sustainable development goals: assessing the impact of car makers on sustainability	Content analysis	A	Qualitative content analysis of GRI 300 Guidelines on Environmental Standards and Sustainability Reports of a sample of 30 companies.	All	0
Gomez-Trujillo et al., 2021	Responsible patterns of production and consumption: The race for the achievement of SDGs in emerging markets	Content analysis	A	Unspecified text analysis of the annual sustainability reports of a sample of 854 companies	12	0
Bojarska et al., 2021	Life cycle assessment as tool for realization of sustainable development goals-towards sustainable future of the world: Mini review	Literature review	A	Literature review	All	5
Berger et al., 2021	Advancing the Water Footprint into an Instrument to Support Achieving the SDGs – Recommendations from the “Water as a Global Resources” Research Initiative (GROW)	Literature review & Conceptual Development	A	Literature review and compilation of recommendations	2,6,7,12	11
Wilson, 2021	Making Information Measurement Meaningful: UN's Sustainable Development Goals and the Social and Human Capital Protocol	Literature review & Conceptual Development	A	Literature review and theoretical conceptualisation	Social - Not specified	0
Vanham & Mekonnen, 2021	The scarcity-weighted water footprint provides unreliable water sustainability scoring	Conceptual Development	A	Comparison of the performance of the scarcity-weighted water footprint indicator Vs. other alternative metrics.	6	22
Hacking, 2019	The SDGs and the sustainability assessment of private-sector projects: theoretical conceptualization and comparison with current practice using the case study of the Asian Development Bank	Literature review & Conceptual Development	A	Literature review and theoretical development	All	23
Jarosch et al., 2020	A Regional Socio-Economic Life Cycle Assessment of a Bioeconomy Value Chain	Analysis of geographic and industry data	B	Application of the RESPONSA socio-economic life cycle assessment framework to a laminated lumber value chain.	1,4,5, 8, 9,10, 16	14
Secher et al., 2018	Construction Product Declarations and Sustainable Development Goals for Small and Medium Construction Enterprises	Literature review & Conceptual Development	B	Theoretical exploration of the applicability life cycle assessment methods to small and medium companies of the construction industry	All	13
Becchetti et al., 2021	Multi-stakeholder impact environmental indexes: The case of NeXt	Conceptual Development	B	Theoretical exploration of the suitability of the NeXt Index, a “living” multi-stakeholder community-based indicator, to SDG impact evaluation.	4,7,8,9,10,11,12,16	0
Giannetti et al., 2022	Enhancing the Assessment of Cleaner Production Practices for Sustainable Development: The Five-Sector Sustainability Model Applied to Water and Wastewater Treatment Companies	Case Study	B	Application of the 5SEnSU model - a framework based on the input–state–output sustainability model- to assess the SDG impact of twenty water and wastewater treatment companies.	3,6,8,12, 13,14	0
Prieto-Egido et al., 2022	Impacts of Information and Communication Technologies on the SDGs: the case of	Conceptual Development & Case Study	B	Combination of the Theory of Change method with the Digital-for-Development paradigm to evaluate the impact on the SDGs of the provision of	All	3

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Authors	Title	Methods	Group	Methodology description	SDGs covered	Citations-WoS databases
	Mayu Telecomunicaciones in rural areas of Peru.			telecommunication services in rural areas. Analyzes interviews, websites, and documents through qualitative content analysis.		
Santos & Moreira, 2021	Social Sustainability of Water and Waste Management Companies in Portugal	Case Study	B	Application of basic economic indicators for assessing of the social sustainability of water and waste management companies.	Social - Not specified	2
Mansell et al., 2020	Development of a New Business Model to Measure Organizational and Project-Level SDG Impact—Case Study of a Water Utility Company	Case Study	B	Application of the Infrastructure SDG Impact-Value Chain framework to assess the SDG impact of a water utility	All	4
van der Waal & Thijssens, 2020	The innovative contribution of multinational enterprises to the Sustainable Development Goals	Conceptual Development	C	Development of a method to evaluate the impact of firm innovations combining the use of a patent classification system and descriptive statistics	All	22
Mottet et al., 2020	Assessing Transitions to Sustainable Agricultural and Food Systems: A Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE)	Conceptual development	C	Development of TAPE tool through a participatory process. The framework developed combines a series of thematic metrics (i.e. economy, governance, health, and nutrition) based mainly on the SDGs indicators.	1,2,5,8	9
Medina-Muñoz, 2020	Corporate social responsibility for poverty alleviation: An integrated research framework	Literature review & Conceptual Development	C	Development of a novel evaluation framework that combines content analysis and assessment against a scale (not yet developed) for evaluating CSR impacts on poverty alleviation.	1	12
Costa et al., 2022	The Degree of Contribution of Digital Transformation Technology on Company Sustainability Areas	Literature review & Conceptual Development & Case Study	C	Systematic literature review + development and application of a method to analyze the SDG impacts of firms' adoption of a series of digital technologies	All	1
Sætra, 2021	A Framework for Evaluating and Disclosing the ESG Related Impacts of AI with the SDGs	Conceptual Development	C	Development of a theoretical framework to evaluate the impact of the corporate adoption of artificial intelligence on the SDGs	All	3
Buonocore et al., 2019	Metrics for the sustainable development goals: renewable energy and transportation	Conceptual Development	C	Development of metrics based on publicly-available country-level data to evaluate the impacts of investments in electricity generation and land transport on SDG 3, 7, 9 and 13.	7,9, 3, 13	19
Deamer et al., 2021	Building Sustainability Impacts from the Bottom Up: Identifying Sustainability Impacts throughout a Geotechnical Company	Conceptual Development	C	Development of a framework based on the combination of process mapping and a pedigree matrix to evaluate the SDG impact of geotechnical engineering companies.	All	0
Abualtaher et al., 2021	Systemic Insights on the Integration of UN Sustainable Development Goals within the Norwegian Salmon Value Chain	Conceptual Development & Case Study	C	Development of a framework to evaluate and manage the SDG impacts of the salmon value chain, based on the Systems Engineering Six-Step Method.	All	0
Hu et al., 2016	Assessing Corporate Sustainability of the ICT sector in Taiwan on the basis of UN Sustainable Development Goals	Conceptual Development & Quantitative content analysis	C	Development of a framework based on SDG compass and KPMG's Industry Matrix to assess the SDG impact of ICT companies.	All	7
Roschangar et al., 2022	Improved iGAL 2.0 Metric Empowers Pharmaceutical Scientists to Make Meaningful Contributions to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12.	Conceptual Development	C	Development of the iGAL 2.0 model for assessing the efficiency of drug synthesis processes.	12	4
Wang et al., 2022	Supporting the Sustainable Development Goals: A context-sensitive indicator for sustainable use of water at the facility level	Conceptual Development	C	Development of an indicator to assess water use at the facility level	6	0
Eberle et al., 2022	Assessing the contribution of products to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals: a methodological proposal	Conceptual Development	C	Development of a social life cycle impact assessment method for assessing the impact of products on the 169 SDG targets.	All	0

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